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Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs
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From: N■■■ A■■■ a A■■■

September 30th, 2021

Memorandum on the “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values” Bill 2021

Thank you for the opportunity to comment on the bill named “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021”, referred to in the following as “bill”.

As a Ghanaian citizen, I understand the role of Parliament to make decisions that are beneficial to the country and fellow Ghanaians. After all, chapter 6 of the 1992 Constitution states in article 35 (1) that “... *sovereignty resides in the people of Ghana from whom Government derives all its powers and authority through this Constitution*”.

The main concern I have concerning the bill is that there are no tangible benefits to be derived from it, but it creates several risks. These risks include worsened living conditions for people identifying as LGBTQ++, as well as threats to our democratic values and international reputation. I am therefore arguing for not passing this bill.

Lack of benefits

With many challenges in the country, it is important to make sure that new laws have a significant benefit for society. Concerning the bill, no real benefits are identifiable to me. As the Constitution states in Chapter 5, section 18 (2): “*No person shall be subjected to interference with the privacy of his home, property*”. What kind of sexual intercourse people have is none of other’s business if it doesn’t harm other persons. The existence of LGBTQ ++ Ghanaians does not threaten heterosexual men or women in Ghana. LGBTQ++ Ghanaians are a minority in Ghana, and do not pose a threat to fertility rates, morals, or economy. In contrary, many contribute to bringing the country forward. With no tangible benefits, I strongly question the need for the proposed bill.

Risks for LGBTQ Ghanaians

The bill in Section 6 (1) lists the people it seeks to punish for their identity and/or sexuality. This is in contradiction with the 1992 Constitution (Amendments in 1996) Chapter 5 article 12 (2): “*Every person in Ghana, whatever his race, place of origin, political opinion, colour, religion, creed or gender shall be entitled to the fundamental human rights and freedoms of the individual contained in this Chapter but subject to respect for the rights and freedoms of others and for the public interest*”. Further, the Constitution in chapter 17 (2) states that “*A person shall not be discriminated against on grounds of gender, ...*”, whilst (3) “*discriminate means to give different treatment to different*

persons attributable only or mainly to their respective descriptions by ... gender, ... whereby persons of one description are subjected to disabilities or restrictions to which persons of another description are not made subject or are granted privileges or advantages which are not granted to persons of another description”.

Counting together sections 20 and 21 of the bill, it is probable that persons arrested may ask for so called “medical help or treatment” to prevent arrest. This kind of conversion therapy has been defined as torture by the Independent Forensic Expert Group (2020)¹. Ghana has decided not to practice torture, as stated in Chapter 5, article 15 (2a) of our Constitution: “*No person shall, whether or not he is arrested, restricted or detained, be subjected to torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, b. any other condition that detracts or is likely to detract from his dignity and worth as a human being*”. Further medical intervention for intersex children is proposed in section 23, which would violate those children’s human rights to the highest attainable standard of health.

Whilst the Constitution in Chapter 6, article 35 (2) clearly mandates the State to “*...seek the well-being of all her citizens protect all Ghanaians*”, this bill creates a risk to LGBTQ++ Ghanaians, including arrest for their identity and torture. Further, as Amnesty International stated, the passing of the bill will increase hatred and intolerance against those fellow Ghanaians².

Threat to democratic values

In Sections 12 and 14, the bill proposes to prohibit any support for LGBTQ persons. This contradicts with the Constitution Chapter 5, article 21 (1a) “*all persons shall have the right to freedom of speech and expression*”. This is a basic democratic value that Members of Parliament should not curtail. After all, the role of the State is described in the Constitution, Chapter Six, article 35 (4) as “*The State shall cultivate among all Ghanaians respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms and the dignity of the human person*”.

In Section 15 and 16, the bill proposes to prohibit forming any kind of association in support for LGBTQ++ topics. This again contradicts with our Constitution Chapter 5, article 21 (1d) “*freedom of assembly including freedom to take part in processions and demonstrations*” and (1e) “*freedom of association, which shall include freedom to form or join trade unions or other associations, national and international, for the protection of their interest*”.

Limiting citizens human rights in order to shape their values is not a democratic practice. Instead, this is a measure that autocratic leaders have been observed to take. As a citizen, I strongly call upon MPs to not support this kind of endeavour.

Threat to international relations

Ghana is internationally known as a successful democratic state, a success story on the African continent. This pushes many tourists who come to our beautiful country because they feel

¹ Independent Forensic Expert Group (2020): Statement on conversion therapy. In *Journal of forensic and legal medicine* 72, p. 101930. DOI: 10.1016/j.jflm.2020.101930.

² Amnesty International (2021): Ghana: Anti-LGBTI Bill Stirs up Hatred, Persecution and Discrimination. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/afr28/4677/2021/en/> last retrieved 30.09.2021

Ghana is a safe and open-minded place to visit. This bill though, is a risk to democracy and thus to tourism. Further, Ghana would disregard several international agreements by passing this bill. Passing this bill would give other nations a good reason to minimise relationships, cooperation, and trade with Ghana, as the State would prove to be unreliable in adhering to signed international agreements.

Conclusion

Summing it up, I have commented on several reasons why this bill poses a risk to Ghanaian society, namely the security of our fellow Ghanaian LGBTQ++ persons, fostering hate and division in society, decreasing democratic values, and decreasing international respect for Ghana. I therefore call upon all Members of Parliament to not pass this bill.

Best and hopeful regards,

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